

It would not be a great exaggeration to say that quantum mechanics is linear algebra, which was given a physical interpretation.

When you compress an image, take a photo of something with your smartphone, watch a video on your laptop, or play a video game, you are using technologies that use various elements from linear algebra. Linear algebra, in turn, is built on two basic elements - a matrix and a vector.

Linear algebra is essential in many areas of computer science because linear equations are easy to solve. It allows you to bring a large set of problems to matrix form, and as a result we solve the matrix.

Mathematical methods and tools in the digital economy

The aggravation of problems with the use of mathematics in economics as digitalization progresses looks somewhat paradoxical, given that digitalization itself is based on mathematics, and economists had enough problems with mathematics before (how many more?).

Nevertheless, this is true, since digitalization has led to changes in a number of relationships in the economy, including changes in the relationships between different types of transaction costs, between fixed and variable costs, but most importantly, attention has become the scarcest resource.

Digital economy as an economy of attention

The term “digital economy” was coined in 1994 by Don Tapscott, emphasizing the increasing role of digital information and its impact on the way business is conducted.

The term “attention economy,” which appeared around the same time, emphasizes another important aspect of the same process - the growing role of attention as a scarce resource, for which there is an increasingly fierce struggle between various market agents, including new and traditional media, as well as various kinds of resellers and traders of other people's attention.

To date, it has been practically proven that the attention of the target audience is the scarcest and therefore most important resource of the modern economy. Therefore, we should take seriously the statements of a number of scientists that the modern economy and, especially, the economy of the future should be called not the digital economy, but the economy of attention.

Of course, advertising and propaganda have existed for a long time, but now the situation is qualitatively has changed thanks to the development of network technologies and the use of artificial intelligence.

With the advent of technical means of collecting, processing and transmitting data, their volume is growing at a previously unimaginable pace. At the same time, new tools for their processing are appearing. But a person's ability to perceive new information, even in the most convenient form for perception, is limited.

And even before you perceive information, you need to pay attention to it. Here human capabilities are even more severely limited, and the flow of information is constantly increasing.

The consumer's natural desire to protect himself from an excessive flow of, as a rule, unnecessary information gives rise to new ways of handling information, including different ways of “understanding texts without reading,” but actively using technical means.

Also, of course, an old, reliable technique is used - visualization. Showing a picture is often more advantageous than proving it using facts and logic.

Therefore, complex mathematical models of the economy are increasingly being replaced by agent-based models with greater visualization capabilities. In general, the problem remains, and new problems are also emerging: difficulties in learning, an abundance of fake news, and so on.

Consumer behavior is increasingly deviating from the classical scheme, according to which he is completely rational, and his choice can be described using some task to maximize "utility". In addition to the deviations noticed and described earlier by psychologists (Kahneman, 2014), new phenomena are discovered, including those that are very reminiscent of interference (Orrell, 2019), which gives grounds to talk about wave effects.

If we look at the same situation from the side of manufacturers and retailers, then the main task is to force a potential consumer, at a minimum, to pay attention to their product (product or service).

Accordingly, marketing tasks are increasingly shifting towards the fight for consumer attention by a variety of means, among which not the least role is played by technical means and techniques that border on abuse or cross this border.

For example, supermarkets install many surveillance cameras, and the arrangement of goods on shelves is regularly changed. At the same time, regular customers find themselves in the situation of newcomers, but differ from them in that they have discount store cards.

Wandering in search of goods that are not on the usual shelf, such a buyer is constantly under surveillance by cameras. His face is easily recognized, and then he presents his discount card at the checkout. At this point, the history of his eyes wandering around the store shelves is added to the already existing dossier on him.

Of course, the buyer also accumulates impressions from his wanderings, seeing products that he otherwise would not have paid attention to or would not even have seen them, since he would have immediately walked to the desired shelf and removed the desired product from it.

In this game, a team of IT specialists from a supermarket presents themselves as benefactors, but in reality plays with the consumer, stealing his attention and time. The quality of the product or service offered in this game also matters, but its role is constantly decreasing, while an increasingly significant role is played by the ability to grab attention and hold it for at least a few seconds, and during these seconds manage to communicate something that will "catch » potential buyer.

This cannot be done without technical means, digital technologies and - as the "cherry on the cake" - artificial intelligence. Of course, huge amounts of information about "their" consumers, accumulated by companies using technical means, are of great value to them.

They categorically do not want to share it with anyone, including not only other companies, but also consultants who help them solve their own problems.

Business leaders, no matter what their title, use the services of both their own advisers and consultants brought in for a specific case. Both sign confidentiality agreements or trade secret disclosure agreements, and therefore are very limited in publicly demonstrating their specialized knowledge.

But they can speak out publicly precisely on those issues where they are not entirely specialists are

not allowed to access sensitive information, and none of the decision makers are going to listen to them.

Or, as an option, business consultants write books where information is revealed exactly to the point where it should become clear to the reader - potential client. where exactly he should turn for advice in case of problems.

The consultant works to improve business efficiency and competitiveness of today's client, and therefore objectively against his competitors. At the same time, he himself gains experience and learns from the client.

Then I really want to share this experience with new clients, and I want to share my experience with them for a good reward even more. That's why not everyone and not always are frank with consultants.

But that's not all. Products and services themselves are becoming increasingly digital. Therefore, we should take quite seriously Michael Goldhaber's idea that, in the limit, the share material costs in the production of goods may become negligible.

On the one hand, this is caused by an increase in the volume of software in complex products, on the other hand, by the emergence of new materials, improvements in processing technologies and other useful manifestations of scientific and technological progress.

Of course, in a real economy things will not reach such a limit. But theoretically it is as natural to consider such an economy as an economy without transaction costs, which was called the Coase economy.

Therefore, one should not take too ironically Michael Goldhaber's idea of turning attention into a kind of currency of the future, having both independent value and serving as a means of payment.

The economy of the future, according to Goldhaber, is an economy of digital products and services, where attention is the means of payment, and "stars" (celebrities) play leading roles. Of course, we are talking about a limiting case, such as, for example, physics without friction.

But to a large extent, such an economy is already being formed. It is almost impossible not to notice this anymore. And then the next quite logical question arises: what mathematics is suitable for modeling such an economy.

The question of a mathematical apparatus for modeling the digital economy, or (taking into account the above) for the economy of attention, can be posed more specifically:

1. Mathematics based on ordinary arithmetic or tropical mathematics (based on idempotent arithmetic)?
2. Classical Boltzmann statistics or quantum statistics, and if quantum, then Bose statistics Einstein or Fermi-Dirac?
3. Ordinary probabilities or probability amplitudes, as in quantum physics?

The answer to any of these three questions depends very much on the audience for whom it is intended. Such questions will almost certainly not trouble econophysicists.

The applicability of Bose-Einstein statistics in economics, primarily to finance, is a provable fact, provable both theoretically and practically. But to what extent this extends to digital products - a

question that is far from obvious.

On the one hand, clones of digital products are practically indistinguishable unless they are artificially labeled, which makes them similar to bosons, money, company shares and other objects for which Bose-Einstein statistics are suitable.

On the other hand, digital products do not have an analogue of the most important property of bosons - be present in any quantity at the same energy level. Money or shares can be in any quantity in the same hands, this is what makes them similar to bosons.

With digital products things are a little different. A digital product is cloned; it is pointless to talk about producing a digital product in any quantity, since the number of clones can theoretically be any.

And here a certain fork in the road arises in terms of formalization. One can understand a digital product as a public good, forgetting that the distribution of such a good is by no means automatic.

But you can be aware that we live in an economy of attention, it is the scarcest resource, and therefore creating a digital product is only the first, and not the most difficult step, the most difficult thing is to draw the attention of the target audience to it.

There is another side to this problem. Having two identical digital products, for example, two identical programs on the same computer, is at a minimum pointless, and often impossible. It turns out that there is a similarity here with fermions, for which the Pauli ban exists, than with bosons, to which this ban does not apply. Therefore, Fermi-Dirac statistics may be suitable for digital product economics.

Moreover, there are quite good reasons to believe that attention largely has wave properties; interference and other phenomena of a wave nature are possible here. Therefore, the apparatus of mathematical modeling in economics needs to be expanded by adopting structures and techniques from quantum physics, despite technical and psychological difficulties.

The quantum approach to economics is inspired by the empirical fact that the monetary system exhibits quantum properties such as discreteness, uncertainty, entanglement, etc. Therefore, as Feynman put it, the simulation must be quantum mechanical in the sense that it reflects these properties (even if it does not directly use quantum formalism).

So the point is not that a quantum approach will be the best method for modeling every aspect of the economy, but that the economy has quantum properties that may need to be taken into account (explicitly or implicitly) depending on the context.

An example from physics: weather forecasters do not base their models on quantum mechanics, but they do base them on the complex properties of water that arise from quantum mechanics. So the main lesson here is that the quantum properties of water molecules lead to very complex emergent properties at the global level that resist descent to a lower level.

Therefore, in economic modeling we can conclude that economic behavior should be modeled at an appropriate level, then quantum properties do not stick out. On the other hand, in physics, technology such as the atomic bomb scales quantum properties to the macro level.

Likewise, money is a developed technology, and its properties are sometimes extended to affect the economy as a whole, for example through phenomena such as the creation of money by private

banks.

You can think of the market as a Hilbert space in which the price of an asset is known precisely only at the moment of the transaction. Ownership and context are important, so an asset bought by one person at one price is different from the same asset bought by another person at a different price.

As in quantum cognition, the act of measuring the price of an asset - in this case by purchasing or sales - affects the price. By constructing the corresponding Hamiltonian equation, we can study the dynamics of market evolution.

As in physics, the complexity of a system means that macro-level behavior is often characterized by emergent properties that cannot be reduced to some lower level.

Again, this differs from the classical approach, which assumes that assets have a certain intrinsic value independent of context; money plays no important role except as an indicator; and calculations can be based on microfoundations individual utility optimization.

Like quantum cognition, quantum finance has become a significant area of research, with many works showing empirical results. Assuming that markets are large and nearly efficient, the results tend to approach those obtained with the classical approach.

Indeed, researchers have so far largely tended to adhere to classical assumptions, such as efficiency, in an attempt to reproduce known results.

However, quantum effects become more important for markets that are thinly traded, and the quantum approach can also be used to describe markets driven by investor sentiment, where there is a significant degree of entanglement between market participants.

While quantum finance focuses on the specialized case of financial markets and is used to study the properties of assets such as stocks or bonds, the same methodology can in principle be extended to describe markets in general and serve as the basis for the mathematical description of quantum economics.

Again, money plays a special role as an asset with a fixed price, and the price of everything else is uncertain unless measured through monetary transactions.

Any activity of a modern person is integrally connected with information. At the moment, it is a strategic resource of society that requires reliable methods of protection against unauthorized access. However, despite the large number of existing ways to ensure information security, new threats to information security regularly arise.

One of these threats is quantum computing, which, no matter how paradoxical it may sound, at the same time as a threat, provides new ways to protect information, giving birth to a new direction in information security - quantum cryptography.

Quantum computing as a threat to information security

Today, most of the information that is transmitted through transmission channels data is encrypted using public key cryptographic systems. The operating principle of these systems is to use two keys. The public key is used to encrypt the original message.

It is published in the public domain. The private or secret key is used when decryption of the received message. Since the late 1970s, the most commonly used public key system has been the RSA algorithm.

Let's briefly look at the operating principle of this algorithm. When a message is encrypted, it is raised to a power modulo N . The resulting encrypted message is transmitted over unsecured communication channels.

To decrypt the received message, you need to use the Euler function of the number N , for which you need to know the prime factors of N . Thus, to decrypt the message, the attacker needs to factor the number N .

The strength of the RSA algorithm is based on the fact that factorization of large numbers is a very complex mathematical problem for which there is still no effective solution algorithm. This is why this public key cryptographic system has long been considered one of the most secure of all encryption systems.

However, in 1994, the American scientist Peter Shor developed a quantum factorization algorithm (Shor's algorithm). The resulting quantum algorithm, unlike classical algorithms, copes with the factorization problem in polynomial time. Based on this fact, Shor's algorithm can be used to crack RSA.

Thus, as soon as a quantum computer consisting of 1000 qubits or more is created, all information encrypted by the RSA algorithm will be instantly compromised, which will jeopardize the information security of society and, in particular, cryptography.

Entangled states

Entanglement is a special quantum form of correlations of composite systems, which does not have a classical analogue, which arises in a system consisting of two or more interacting subsystems (or previously interacted and then separated), and is a superposition of alternative (mutually exclusive from the classical point of view) states, which cannot be realized in classical physics.

For such systems, fluctuations of individual parts are interconnected, but not through ordinary interactions through energy exchange (classical correlations), limited, for example, by the speed of light, but through nonlocal quantum correlations, when a change in one part of the system at the same moment in time affects its remaining parts (even separated in space, in the limit and at infinitely large distances).

Mathematically, this is expressed in the fact that the state vector of the system, as a whole, cannot be represented as a product (tensor) of the state vectors of its subsystems.

In this case, it is impossible to divide the system into local objects and say that this is one object, and this is another. There is always some part of the system that belongs to both objects equally. The subsystems are intertwined, entangled with each other like Siamese twins, and form a single whole, even if only in some insignificant part.

Description of such systems within the framework of a "local objective theory", which assumes the existence of independent objects, becomes impossible. More precisely, classical physics can be considered as some approximation in describing physical reality, when quantum correlations are insignificant compared to those classical correlations on which we focus our attention, i.e. on those physical characteristics of the system that characterize the local object.

For example, if you take conjoined twins, classical physics will be able to describe the characteristics of each of the twins separately, and such a description will be somewhat reasonable.

But with such a description it will be impossible to take into account the most important thing, that such twins are inextricably linked to each other, even by the most insignificant part of their body, and cannot, for example, move independently of each other.

Although, according to the classic description, nothing prohibits them from being in different rooms. Agree, the value of such a description immediately drops sharply.

In contrast, quantum mechanics can describe an object both as a single whole and as its individual local parts. The classical description becomes, at the same time, a special case of a quantum mechanical description, when individual properties of the entire system as a whole are deliberately excluded.

With this approach, it is already possible to understand for what purpose and for what the classical approach is used, not forgetting the limits of its applicability, and that such a description provides comprehensive information about the object.

One might get the misleading impression that since quantum correlations in the macroscopic world are negligible, they can be completely ignored. Classical physics does just that.

But this does not take into account one significant circumstance - the properties of these correlations are so unusual, surprising and comprehensive that they can easily “outweigh” the strongest classical correlations. By neglecting quantum correlations, classical physics, as a result, sharply limits its capabilities in describing physical reality, reducing it to almost an infinitesimal part of the entire total quantum reality.

Hence the inability of classical physics to describe a huge number of “supernatural” phenomena. Gradually, an understanding of this circumstance comes to the fore, as the closest object of attention of scientists, quantum correlations of entangled states of a system.

One of the main achievements of quantum theory in recent years is that a transition has been made to a quantitative description of quantum entanglement. Various measures of entanglement were introduced, and it became possible to theoretically calculate these quantities and compare the obtained values with the results of physical experiments.

The need for a quantitative description of quantum entanglement was caused by the fact that entangled states have recently become an important practical resource for many new applied disciplines: quantum computer, quantum cryptography, quantum teleportation, quantum computing physics, etc.

Entangled states have attracted the closest attention of scientists. Gradually, its applied areas emerged as independent sections of quantum theory: the theory of decoherence, the theory of entangled states, quantum theory information.

Modern researchers are attracted to the phenomenon of quantum entanglement because it allows them to purposefully use nonlocal quantum resources of the system for practical needs. Nonlocality is a specific feature of quantum entanglement, and its manifestations appear “magical” from the point of view of classical physics.

The demands of practice and the needs of society for new promising technologies have led science to move from the usual semi-classical Copenhagen interpretation of quantum mechanics, which implies the mandatory presence of a classical observer (measuring device) to a purely quantum approach, in which there is no longer any place for the classical “relic.”

As a result, the quantum approach to describing the surrounding reality has become a self-sufficient coherent theory, built from unified general principles, logically including classical physics as a special case of quantum description.

Another achievement of quantum theory is that the possibility of “manipulating” quantum entanglement has been theoretically proven and experimentally confirmed. The degree of entanglement of a system can be changed, both by increasing it (purification, distillation of entanglement) and decreasing it (dilution of entanglement, decoherence by the environment).

Entanglement is a unique quantum mechanical resource that plays a key role in many of the most exciting applications of quantum computing and quantum information.

Entanglement is considered a fundamental resource of Nature, comparable in importance to energy, information, entropy, or any other fundamental resource. In recent years, enormous efforts have been made to better understand its properties.

Many researchers hope that further study of the properties of entanglement will provide insights that will help develop new applications in the fields of quantum computing and quantum information.

Quantum computing and quantum information make it possible to think about computing physically, and this approach opens up many new possibilities in communications and information processing.

Computer scientists and information theorists have a fruitful new paradigm for research. Any physical theory, not just quantum mechanics, can serve as the basis for the theory of information processing and communication theory.

As a result of these studies, information processing devices can be created, far superior to modern computing and communication systems in their capabilities, which will have its positive and negative consequences for the entire society.

Creation and transformation of entanglement is an important dynamical process in quantum information theory

Entanglement represents another elementary static resource of quantum mechanics. Its properties differ from the properties of resources familiar mainly from classical information theory. Let us consider two theoretical theories well known in the literature. information problems associated with confusion.

The creation of entanglement is a simple dynamic process studied in quantum information theory, within which problems are solved:

Definitions of the number of qubits that two parties must exchange in order to create a given entangled state shared between them, given that they did not previously share any entanglement: determination of the content of the dynamic process representing the transformation of entanglement from one form to another.

An example of a Bell state is considered, which is divided between the sender and receiver of information, which they want to transform into an entangled state of some other type.

In this case, problems arise:

- determination of the required resource to perform the task of transforming into an entangled state;
- solving a given problem without establishing a connection between the sender and the recipient;
- determination of the number of quantum transmissions in the presence of quantum communication.

Solving these problems of creating and transforming entanglement leads to the formation of an independent field of research in the field of quantum computing.

For example, distributed quantum computing can be viewed simply as a method of creating entanglement between two or more parties; then the lower limits on the number of transfers required to perform such a distributed quantum computation are determined by the lower limits on the number of transfers required to create suitable entangled states.

Quantum information theory is the most abstract part of the field of quantum computing and quantum information, and in some ways the most fundamental.

The development of quantum information theory and, ultimately, the entire field of quantum computing and quantum information raises the following problematic questions:

- what makes information processing possible?
- what separates the quantum and classical worlds?
- what resources, unavailable in the classical world, can be used in quantum computing?

Options for solving these problems today require further research into the clarity representation, capabilities and development of quantum information processing processes.

Using quantum computing as a means of protecting information

The threat of quantum computing has given rise to new approaches to information security. The first approach, post-quantum cryptography, proposes the use of encryption algorithms based on mathematical problems that are difficult for both classical and quantum calculations.

The second approach – quantum cryptography – uses the basic laws of quantum mechanics to ensure the secrecy of information. In quantum cryptography, the following main areas can be distinguished: technologies for quantum data transfer; quantum key distribution technologies; quantum encryption; quantum digital signature technologies, quantum hashing technologies.

It has been mathematically proven that quantum data transmission channels are the most secure, which allows for a new level of information protection. The carrier of information, which is encrypted using the laws of quantum mechanics, in this case will be a quantum object, for example, a photon.

According to the fundamental laws of quantum physics, measuring a quantum object or any other impact on it leads to a change in its state. It follows from this that an attempt to intercept a message or eavesdrop on a channel will lead to a change in the state of the photon, which will immediately become known to the recipient.

Quantum data transmission channels are the basis for the implementation of quantum key

distribution algorithms - the main direction in the development of quantum cryptography.

Quantum key distribution technology allows you to distribute keys between remote users over open communication channels, based on the laws of quantum physics.

QKD technology is based on the impossibility of copying unknown quantum conditions; inability to listen to the signal; the impossibility of absolutely reliably distinguishing between two non-orthogonal quantum states.

All quantum key distribution protocols work according to the following principle: Alice (the sender) sets the quantum states of photons and transmits them via quantum data channels. Bob (the receiver) receives the photons and records their states.

If Alice and Bob have not agreed in advance which type of photon polarization will be chosen, then Bob will destroy the received signal. Alice and Bob will be able to determine whether eavesdropping took place during the transfer of the key by comparing the transmitted and received data. The comparison method is determined by each quantum key distribution protocol.

The main requirement for absolutely strong ciphers is that the key for it must be equal in length to or greater than the length of the encoded message.

Quantum cryptography is a rapidly developing branch of information security. Based on the laws of physics, quantum cryptography is one of the most reliable ways to protect information.

Thank you for your attention